

Infectious aetiologies of neonatal illness in south Asia classified using WHO definitions: a primary analysis of the ANISA study

Article summary

Neonatal mortality constitutes nearly half of all deaths among children under five globally. Over one-third of these neonatal deaths occur in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan, where severe infections are a leading cause. Diagnosing neonatal infections is challenging due to non-specific symptoms, and the issue is exacerbated in low-resource settings due to limited diagnostic capabilities. In such settings, first-level health workers often use the WHO's Integrated Management of Childhood Illnesses (IMCI) algorithm to assess young infants (0–59 days old) and determine whether treatment or referral is necessary.

While the IMCI strategy is widely implemented, some families in low-resource regions refuse referral advice for seriously ill infants, while others hospitalize infants unnecessarily for minor illnesses. To address barriers in implementing the IMCI recommendation for 7 days of hospital-based antibiotic treatment for possible serious bacterial infections—and based on evidence supporting simplified treatments for non-critically ill infants when referral is declined—WHO updated its guidelines in 2015. These revisions introduced simplified antibiotic regimens (2–7 days of injections followed by 5–7 days of oral antibiotics) and categorized cases of serious bacterial infection by severity, tailoring treatments accordingly.

The updated guidelines recommend outpatient oral antibiotics for infants with fast breathing as their sole symptom (the least severe illness). Infants with clinical severe infection, resembling the original 1996 case definition of serious bacterial infection, are treated with simpler regimens if referral is not feasible. Critically ill infants require hospital referral for intravenous antibiotics and supportive care, preceded by a pre-referral antibiotic dose.

The 2015 guideline was largely based on low-quality evidence, with a notable gap in linking infectious causes, clinical case definitions, and management recommendations. The Aetiology of Neonatal Infections in South Asia (ANISA) study (2010–2014) sought to fill this gap by investigating the incidence, causes, and antibiotic resistance profiles of community-

acquired infections among over 5000 infants in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan. Diagnostic tests identified causative agents in 28% of cases meeting the possible serious bacterial infection criteria.

In this analysis of the ANISA cohort, researchers re-categorized neonatal illnesses using the 2015 WHO case definitions (critical illness, clinical severe infection, and fast breathing) and evaluated their effectiveness in identifying bacterial infections. They also examined the proportion of clinical severe infections attributable to bacterial or viral causes and explored whether specific clinical signs could predict bacterial infection.

Figure 1

The ANISA study (2011–2014) estimated pathogen prevalence in 4000 infants with clinical severe infection using a partial latent class model. Approximately 71.7% of cases (95% credible interval: 68.9–74.5) were classified as "other or none," including infections not linked to specific pathogens or bacteria identified through blood cultures but not covered by the ANISA diagnostic panel.

Figure 2

Shows estimates from a partial latent class model of pathogen prevalence in infants with critical illness (n=992) or clinical severe infection (n=4000) based on data from the ANISA study (2011–2014). This category includes bacterial infection episodes not attributed to any pathogen class in the ANISA model, including bacteria grown on blood cultures but without a corresponding test in the ANISA diagnostic panel.

Figure 3

Presents estimates from a partial latent class model on pathogen prevalence in infants with isolated fast breathing (n=771) and those meeting the clinical severe infection case definition (n=1552) with late-onset disease (3–59 days post-birth), based on data from the ANISA study (2011–2014). This category includes bacterial infection episodes not assigned to any pathogen class in the model, including bacteria identified in blood cultures without a corresponding test in the ANISA molecular diagnostic panel.

Table 1

The table presents the symptoms in infants who reached the age of developing type 2 diabetes, 2011–2014.

Authors

Shamim A Qazi is a pediatrician with more than 40 years of expertise in infectious diseases, clinical research, and implementation studies. He worked for 20 years in the Maternal, Newborn, Child, and Adolescent Health (MNCH) Department at WHO in Geneva before retiring.

Gary L. Darmstadt is an expert in maternal and child health, currently serving as the Associate Dean for Maternal and Child Health at Stanford University School of Medicine. He is also a professor and co-director of Global Pediatric Research in the Department of Pediatrics. Darmstadt has had an extensive career in global health, including roles as Senior Fellow at the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and Director of the International Center for Maternal and Newborn Health at Johns Hopkins. He has contributed significantly to WHO's advisory groups, including on Kangaroo Mother Care and guidelines for the care of preterm infants. His research and work focus on improving maternal and child health outcomes globally.

Dr. Mohammad Shahidul Islam is a professor at the Institute of Information Technology, Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh. His research primarily focuses on image processing, pattern recognition, and telecommunications. He has a Google Scholar h-index of 8, indicating that eight of his published papers have each been cited at least eight Times.

Daniel E Roth is a physician and researcher specializing in pediatric infectious diseases, global health, and nutrition. He is affiliated with the Department of Paediatrics at the Hospital for Sick Children (SickKids) in Toronto. Dr. Roth has made significant contributions to child health research, particularly focusing on nutrition and growth in low-resource settings. His H-index is 104, reflecting a substantial academic impact with numerous highly-cited publications in the field.

Dr. Zulfiqar A. Bhutta is a global health expert and professor at Aga Khan University, specializing in maternal, child, and adolescent health. He is also Co-Director at the SickKids Centre for Global Child Health. With over 1,275 publications and a remarkable H-index of 203, his research has had a significant global impact. He has been a key figure in global health initiatives and has received numerous prestigious awards, including the Roux Prize and the John Dirks Canada Global Health Award.

Pinaki Panigrahi is a renowned pediatric infectious disease expert with a focus on gut microbiota and its role in health outcomes like sepsis and necrotizing enterocolitis in newborns. He spent 25 years at the University of Maryland before joining Georgetown University Medical Center, where he leads international microbiome research. Panigrahi's work has had a significant impact on childhood diseases, especially in low-resource settings, with studies funded by institutions like NIH and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation.

Dr. Daniel Westreich is a Professor of Epidemiology at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, specifically at the Gillings School of Global Public Health. He earned his PhD in Epidemiology from UNC-Chapel Hill in 2008. His research focuses on the intersection of HIV and reproductive health, particularly in understanding how pregnancy and contraceptive methods affect HIV outcomes. He is also engaged in studying HIV-related chronic diseases and COVID-19. Dr. Westreich is known for his work in causal inference and epidemiologic methods for implementation science. He authored *Epidemiology By Design: A Causal Approach to the Health Sciences* and serves as an associate editor for the *American Journal of Epidemiology*. His H-index is 57.

Stephanie J. Schrag, DPhil, is a prominent researcher specializing in infectious diseases and epidemiology, particularly related to neonatal infections and prevention. She is affiliated with the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), where she has made significant contributions, such as in the area of neonatal sepsis prevention. Schrag's work has focused on group B streptococcal disease prevention and surveillance of invasive early-onset neonatal sepsis.

Journal

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